

Ligational behaviour of pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid with nickel(II) in presence of imidazoles

M. Sivasankaran Nair^{*a} and M. A. Neelakantan^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627 012, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, National Engineering College, K. R. Nagar, Kovilpatti-628 503, India

Manuscript received 10 February 1999, accepted 9 July 1999

The mixed ligand complexes of stoichiometry NiABH, NiAB and NiAB₂ have been detected in the Ni^{II}-pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid(A)-imidazole, -benzimidazole, -histamine and -L-histidine (B) systems. The results indicate that in NiABH species the extra proton resides with ligand B. In NiAB and NiAB₂ complexes, pyd and hist are tridentate, hist is bidentate and him and bim are monodentate.

Organic bases containing pyridine ring are used in small quantities in medicine, but in excess it is poisonous. Investigations on the formation of mixed ligand complexes with pyridine containing ligands are increasingly becoming important^{1,2}. Mixed ligand complexes involving pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid acts as biological models describing the effect of oxgeneous ligands and/or metal ion on the possible enzymatic reactions. The imidazole and benzimidazole rings function as ligands toward transition metal ions in a variety of biologically important molecules including iron heme systems, vitamin B₁₂ and its derivatives³. Here we report a systematic pH-metric studies on the formation of mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} containing pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (pyd) and imidazoles, viz. imidazole (him), benzimidazole (bim), histamine (hist) and L-histidine (his) at 37° and $I = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄). The Ni^{II}-pyd(A) binary system under this experimental conditions has also been studied.

Results and Discussion

Ni^{II}-pyd(A) binary complex equilibria : The binary species of the type NiA and NiA₂ in addition to HA and H₂A species are detected in this system. The log β_{NiA} value of 7.02 in this system is higher than of 6.32 in the Ni^{II}-nca(A) system³. This suggests the tridentate binding of pyd with Ni^{II}. Also, this value is comparable to that of 6.95 reported in the Ni^{II}-dipicolinic acid system¹, where the ligand binds the metal in a tridentate manner. Thus, there would be one 5- and one 6-membered chelate rings in the NiA-pyd complex. A maximum of 80% of the total metal ion has been found to be present in the form of this species in the 1 : 2 solution. In the NiA₂-pyd species both the ligands bind the metal in a tridentate manner forming two 5- and two 6-membered chelate rings giving a coordination number of six to the metal. In a 1 : 2 solution ca 67% of the total metal ion has been found to be present in the form of NiA₂ species.

Mixed ligand complex equilibria

The Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him and -bim(B) systems showed the presence of NiAB and NiAB₂ species, while in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist and -his(B) systems the species NiABH and NiAB have been detected (Table 2). The various binary species due to ligands A and B accounted are given Table 1

Stability and structure of NiAB and NiAB₂ complexes :

The log $K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiB}}$ values computed (Table 2) in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him and -bim(B) systems bear favourable comparison with the log K_1 value (Table 1) in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A) system. Again, the log $K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiA}}/\log K_{\text{NiAB}_2}^{\text{NiA}}$ values in these systems (Table 2) are comparable to the log $K_1/\log K_2$ values in the Ni^{II}-him and -bim(B) binary systems (Table 1). These trends demonstrate that binding of the ligands A and B with Ni^{II} in these systems is similar to that in their respective binary species. Thus the NiAB species in these two systems would be four-coordinated due to the tridentate binding of pyd and monodentate binding of him and bim(B) ligands. In the NiAB₂ species the metal ion would be pentacoordinated due to the tridentate binding of pyd and monodentate binding of two him and bim. About 55% of the total metal ion has been found to be present in the form of NiAB species in both the 1 : 1 · 1 and 1 · 2 · 2 solutions of Ni^{II}, pyd(A) and him(B). Now, the relative stabilities of NiAB₂ and NiAB complexes in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him and -bim(B) systems can be compared. The $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiAB}}$ values (Table 2) are higher than the respective $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiAB}_2}$ values. This demonstrates that NiAB is more stable than the corresponding NiAB₂. This can be explained by considering the fact that if ligand(A) forms more than one chelate ring the stability of NiAB species would be higher than that of NiAB₂ species⁴, i.e. the coordination of pyd(A) results in more than one chelate ring

and this explains higher stability of NiAB species compared to that of NiAB₂ species.

Table 1. Stability constants for the proton and parent binary complexes of Ni^{II} with pyd, him, bim, hist and his(B)^a

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	pyd	him ^a	bim ^b	hist ^a	his ^a
log β _{HB}	4.69(4)	6.55(2)	5.68(1)	9.39(8)	8.96(3)
log β _{H₂B}	7.12(6)	—	—	15.34(1)	14.96(5)
log β _{H₃B}	—	—	—	—	17.37(9)
log β _{NiBH}	—	—	—	11.85(3)	13.08(5)
log β _{NiB}	7.02(5)	3.37(5)	2.37(4)	6.36(2)	8.84(7)
log β _{NiB₂H}	—	—	—	17.86(4)	21.04(7)
log β _{NiB₂}	11.79	5.70(9)	4.11(9)	11.22(2)	15.94(4)
log β _{NiB₃}	—	7.90(9)	—	—	—
log β _{NiB₄}	—	9.57(11)	—	—	—
pK _{NiBH} ^H	—	—	—	5.49	4.24
pK _{NiB₂H} ^H	—	—	—	6.64	5.10
log K _{NiB₂} ^{NiB}	4.77	2.13	1.74	4.86	7.10
log K _{NiB₂H} ^{NiBH}	—	—	—	6.01	7.96
log K _{NiB₃} ^{NiB₂}	—	2.20	—	—	—
log K _{NiB₄} ^{NiB₃}	—	1.67	—	—	—

^apyd becomes ligand A in the mixed ligand systems. ^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 5.

Table 2. Stability constants of the mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him, bim, hist and his(B)

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	Ligand B			
	him	bim	hist	his
log β _{NiABH}	—	—	18.14(2)	19.83(5)
log β _{NiAB}	10.28(4)	9.02(5)	13.31(6)	15.15(7)
log β _{NiAB₂}	11.98(9)	10.02(7)	—	—
pK _{NiABH} ^H	—	—	4.83	4.68
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiA}	3.26	2.00	6.29	8.13
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiB}	6.91	6.66	6.95	6.31
log K _{NiABH} ^{NiBH}	—	—	6.29	6.75
log K _{NiABH} ^{NiA}	—	—	11.12	12.81
log K _{NiAB₂} ^{NiB₂}	6.28	5.91	—	—
Δ log K _{NiABH}	—	—	-0.73	-0.27
Δ log K _{NiAB}	-0.11	-0.36	-0.07	-0.71
Δ log K _{NiAB₂}	-0.74	-1.10	—	—

The log K_{NiAB}^{NiB}/log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} values in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist(B) system (Table 2) bear favorable comparison to the log K₁ values respectively in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A) and Ni^{II}-hist(B) binary systems (Table 1). This demonstrates that in the NiAB species both the ligands pyd(A) and hist(B) bind the metal in a manner similar to their binding in their binary analogues. The log β_{NiAB} value of 13.31 in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist(B) system is higher than the log β_{NiAB₂} value of 11.98 in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him(B) system, though in both the complexes the metal ion has a coordination number of five. This is due to the fact that coordination of hist(B)

ligand in the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist(B) system results in the formation of a 6-membered chelate ring, while the monodentate binding of him(B) in the NiAB₂ species in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-him(B) system results in the formation of no chelate ring. Thus chelate effect is responsible for the higher stability of the former species.

The log β_{NiAB} value of 15.15 in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-his(B) system is still higher than that of 13.31 in the corresponding hist(B) system. This indicates that in the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-his(B) system, his binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner giving the preferred coordination number of six to Ni^{II}. The Δ log K_{NiAB} values obtained in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-B (B = him, bim, hist and his) complexes (Table 2) are slightly negative. This can be explained as follows. Pyd(A) coordinates with Ni^{II} via two carboxylate groups and one pyridine nitrogen. In this case, Ni^{II}-pyd(A) π-interaction is possible. This Ni^{II}-pyd π-interaction results in the shift of π-electron density from the metal to the ligand. Hence, there is an increase in class A character of the Ni^{II} ion on coordination with pyd. Consequently, there is a decrease in the tendency of the ligand B, having π-acid character to combine with NiA. Due to the less tendency of the second π-acid ligand(B) to combine with [Ni-pyd(A)] than [Ni(H₂O)], Δ log K becomes slightly negative.

Stability and structure of NiABH complexes : Formation of NiAB type of species has been found to be more favoured above pH 5.0 in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist and -his(B) systems. In Ni^{II}-pyd(A) no protonated binary species has been detected, while in the Ni^{II}-hist/his(B) system protonated binary species has been identified (Table 1). The pK_{NiABH}^H values calculated in these two systems (Table 2) follow the trends of the respective pK_{NiBH}^H values (Table 1) in the Ni^{II}-hist and -his(B) binary systems. This indicates the possibility of the attachment of the extra proton with ligand B possibly to its amino group as in the case of NiBH/NiB₂H hist and his(B) binary species. This appears to be correct because the log K_{NiABH}^{NiBH} values obtained (Table 2) are comparable to log K₁ value in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A) system. Also, the log K_{NiABH}^{NiA} values (Table 2) for the NiABH species in these systems are comparable to the log K_{NiBH}^{Ni} values in the Ni^{II}-hist/his(B) systems. Thus, in the NiABH species in the Ni^{II}-pyd(A)-hist(B) system the ligand pyd binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner and the protonated hist(B) binds through its imidazole nitrogen. In the corresponding his(B) system the metal ion attains a coordination number of five due to the tridentate and bidentate binding of pyd(A) and protonated his(B) ligands respectively. The Δ log K_{NiABH} values (Table 2) demonstrate high stabilities for the mixed ligand complexes. The species distribution plots have been obtained for all the

systems. In order to indicate the qualitative features observed in these the speciation plots for the Ni^{II} -pyd(A)-hist(B) system at a $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} : \text{pyd} : \text{hist}$ ratio of 1 : 2 : 2 are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for the Ni^{II} -pyd(A)-hist(B) ternary system at $C_M = 0.003$, $C_A = C_B = 0.006$: (1) unbound Ni^{II} , (2) NiA , (3) NiA_2 , (4) NiBH , (5) NiB , (6) NiB_2 , (7) NiABH and (8) NiAB .

Experimental

All the ligands were obtained from Fluka. The metal perchlorate and other reagents were prepared and estimated as described earlier^{4,5}. The apparatus and procedure used

for pH-titration have been described earlier⁴⁻⁶. The auxiliary data in the Ni^{II} -pyd(A) system have been re-determined in the present experimental conditions, while such data in the Ni^{II} -him, bim, hist and his(B) systems have been taken from literature (Table 1)^{4,5}. All the calculations were done with the help of the computer program⁷ MINIQUAD-75 using a HCl HP infinity computer.

References

1. M. M. Khalil, S. A. Mohamed and A. M. Radalla, *Talanta*, 1997, **44**, 1365.
2. M. S. A. Hamza and J. M. Pratt, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1647; M. Kurihara, K. Ozutsumi and T. Kawashima, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 3379; M. R. Ullah and P. K. Battacharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 150; 1991, **30**, 976.
3. R. K. O. Sigel, B. Song and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 744; H. Sigel, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1993, **22**, 255; B. Song, R. K. O. Sigel and H. Sigel, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**, 29; M. A. Neelakantan, Ph.D. Thesis, M. S. University, 1998.
4. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu, M. S. Pillai and C. Natarajan, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 917.
5. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu, M. S. Pillai and C. Natarajan, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 132.
6. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu, M. A. Neelakantan, M. Vincent and M. S. Pillai, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 95.
7. P. Gans, A. Vacca and A. Sabatini, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.